

Interpretable Railway Object Classification using Part-Prototype Networks

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Abstract. Enhancing safety and operational efficiency in railway systems benefits from robust AI-powered perception, particularly for reliable obstacle and pedestrian detection. However, the prevalent black-box nature of contemporary deep learning models presents significant challenges for verification and trust, especially within safety-critical railway environments characterised by dynamic weather, illumination changes, and high speed, which create undesirable effects such as cluttered backgrounds, and motion blur, which may hinder the performance of computer vision approaches. This paper addresses the need for more transparent models by proposing the application of Prototypical Part Networks (ProtoPNet) for interpretable obstacle and pedestrian classification within the railway domain. Experiments with the OSDaR23 dataset demonstrate that training with a careful selection of data augmentation processes enhances key metrics such as precision, recall and F1-score while yielding transparent results with visually robust prototypes.

Keywords: Object Classification, Interpretability, Railway

1 Introduction

The continuous drive towards enhancing safety and operational efficiency within railway systems has spurred significant interest in AI-powered perception technologies, particularly for the realisation of autonomous trains [29]. Among the myriad of perception tasks, the reliable detection of obstacles and pedestrians on or near the railway track stands as a paramount safety function [25, 19]. While contemporary deep learning models have demonstrated substantial capabilities in object recognition, their prevalent *black-box* nature poses considerable challenges [24].

Current methodologies for detecting obstacles and pedestrians in railway environments frequently lack transparency, making verification of the decision-making processes a complex endeavour [31]. The railway context itself introduces a unique confluence of challenges for computer vision systems. These include, but are not limited to, highly dynamic weather patterns, significant and sudden variations in illumination

(e.g. transitions between open tracks and tunnels, day and night operations), visually cluttered and complex backgrounds (comprising elements such as catenary lines, signaling equipment and dense vegetation), and the potential for motion blur due to train speed. These factors can adversely affect not only the raw detection performance but also the consistency and reliability of any perception system. Consequently, there is a pressing need to rigorously evaluate the performance and robustness of models within this demanding operational domain.

Explainable AI (XAI), and more specifically, self-explainable or interpretable models such as Prototypical Part Networks (ProtoPNet) [2], present a promising venue towards achieving transparent and trustworthy systems which can elucidate the internal reasoning of the AI models by providing insights into the *how* and *why* a specific prediction is formulated. Thus, enabling an easier analysis of the behaviour of models under different circumstances, which enables better debugging and reduces complexity in certification processes.

In this paper, we propose the adaptation and application of ProtoPNet for the task of interpretable obstacle and pedestrian detection within a railway environment. The principal contributions of this research are articulated as follows:

- The novel application and systematic adaptation of ProtoPNet for the task of obstacle and pedestrian classification within complex railway environments.
- Comparative analysis of the classification performance of several ProtoPNet configurations.
- Qualitative analysis of the prototypes learned by the model, which leads to discovery of issues that would not be noticed in black-box models.

2 Related Work

The application of advanced image classification techniques, particularly deep learning, holds significant promise for enhancing railway safety and operational efficiency [12]. However, the deployment of such complex models in this safety-critical environment necessitates a thorough understanding of their decision-making processes.

2.1 Explainability and Interpretability Methods

The increasing complexity of AI models, particularly deep neural networks used in image classification tasks, often results in *black-box* systems where the internal decision-making processes are completely opaque. This lack of transparency presents significant hurdles, especially in safety-critical domains where understanding the *why* behind a prediction is crucial for trust, accountability, debugging, and safe deployment [11].

To remedy this opacity, current research has seen an increasing interest in XAI. Explainability often denotes *post-hoc* techniques applied to opaque *black-box* models to produce understandable explanations without altering model architecture. The key challenge here is *fidelity*, ensuring the explanations accurately reflect the model's internal reasoning [10]. Prominent post-hoc techniques include saliency or gradient-based methods like Grad-CAM [26] and its variants (e.g. [18], [1]), which generate

heat-maps highlighting important image regions for a given prediction. Model-agnostic perturbation-based methods, such as LIME [22] and SHAP [17], explain predictions by observing output changes in response to input perturbations, offering local (LIME) or theoretically grounded global/local (SHAP) feature importance values. However, these can be computationally expensive and rely on potentially problematic perturbation strategies [11]. Concept-based explanations, like TCAV [13], aim for a higher-level understanding by quantifying model sensitivity to human-defined concepts, but require concept examples and face challenges like concept entanglement [11]. Counterfactual explanations identify minimal input changes needed to alter a prediction, offering insights into decision boundaries but facing difficulties in generating realistic changes [6].

In contrast, self-explainable models or interpretable models typically refer to models that are inherently transparent: they integrate explainability directly into the model's design and training. These methods aim for inherent faithfulness by tying explanations to the model's mechanisms, addressing the fidelity concerns of post-hoc approaches [10]. Attention mechanisms, adapted from Natural Language Processing architectures, allow models to weight input regions, providing focus maps as inherent explanations, although whether attention truly equates to explanation is debated [11]. Prototype-based learning, exemplified by ProtoPNet [2], uses case-based reasoning, comparing input parts to learned prototypes, which are often patches from images of training data. This offers intuitive "*this looks like that*" explanations, but interpretability depends heavily on the quality and clarity of the learned prototypes. Inherently interpretable concept-based architectures, like Concept Bottleneck Models (CBM) [14], force information through an intermediate layer representing explicit concepts, aiming for transparency in the final concept-to-prediction mapping. However, defining adequate concepts, preventing information leakage, and obtaining concept supervision remain significant issues [5].

2.2 Railway Object Classification

Computer vision has become increasingly vital for enhancing railway safety, maintenance and efficiency [12]. Automated vision systems are replacing traditional manual inspections for tasks like track inspection, obstacle detection, and component monitoring. The systems must be robust to challenging railway conditions and often require real-time processing capabilities [23].

Methodologically, deep learning has become the standard approach, outperforming traditional computer vision techniques. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) of various architectures (e.g. ResNet [9], VGG [27]) are widely used for feature extraction and classification [23].

For tasks requiring localisation, object detection frameworks like Faster R-CNN [21], SSD [15], and YOLO variants [20] are common, with YOLO often favoured for real-time applications.

More recently, Transformer architectures such as Vision Transformer [7] and Swin Transformer [16] are being applied, sometimes in hybrid models with CNNs, leveraging their ability to capture global image dependencies [23].

Traditional computer vision methods involving hand-crafted features such as Histogram of Oriented Gradients [4], and Haar-like features [30], and classifiers such as Support Vector Machines [3] generally show lower performance and robustness in complex railway environments compared to DL methods [23].

Significant challenges remain in railway image classification. Systems must cope with highly variable environmental factors like diverse illumination and adverse weather conditions, as well as motion blur from train speed [12]. Moreover, operational constraints like real-time processing demands and the need for extremely high reliability in safety-critical applications add further complexity. Addressing these challenges is crucial for the trustworthy deployment of AI in railways, highlighting the role of interpretability in validating model reasoning and ensuring reliance on valid features rather than dataset artefacts.

3 System Architecture and Experimental Design

This section details our approach to bridge the gap between model performance and transparency by employing ProtoPNet. ProtoPNet’s architecture is inherently designed for interpretability, offering case-based explanations that resonate with human reasoning (*this part of the scene looks like this known example of an obstacle/pedestrian*). The aim is to develop a system that not only accurately identifies potential hazards but also provides transparent, verifiable justifications for its detections, thereby fostering trust and facilitating robust validation.

3.1 OSDaR23 Dataset

Open Sensor Data for Rail 2023 (OSDaR23) [28] is a multi-sensor dataset created to push automated railway operation research. Recorded in Hamburg, Germany, in September 2021, this dataset incorporates synchronised data from multiple sensors such as RGB cameras, infra-red cameras, LiDAR sensors, radar, and GNSS/IMU data. In addition, it includes manually labelled data of 20 different object classes relevant in railway environments, such as catenary poles, signals, vehicles, and pedestrians.

For the current work, we leverage the annotation within OSDaR23 dataset to extract information pertaining to individual objects. As the original images from this dataset can contain one or more annotated objects, a dedicated pre-processing pipeline was necessary to create a dataset consisting of individual object images. This process involves several steps: first, we extract the unique object identifiers linked to each annotation, then, we obtain precise positional information (bounding box coordinates) for each identified object in each image. Objects annotated with an occlusion level of 50% or higher are subsequently filtered out. Finally, each remaining object is extracted from the original image through cropping based on its spatial information. These crops are performed using two potential methods: either a square crop that includes the surrounding context around the object’s bounding box, or a strict crop precisely defined by the bounding box, to which a black padding is added to ensure a square output image. The choice between these cropping methods is determined by the specific configuration of the model being trained, which will be further discussed in later sections.

Furthermore, during data capture, especially nearing a train station, train speed is decreased without reducing image capture frequency. This provokes an increase in the repetition of objects in subsequent images, which contain the same static objects, and similar poses for dynamic objects such as persons. To reduce this redundancy, we filter image crops of the same object with a process based on the Structural Similarity Index Measure to remove the image crops that exceed a similarity threshold of 0.3, ensuring significant differences between images. This process reduces the initial 67795 image dataset to a smaller set of 5922 relevant images.

After the filtering process is done, we separate the resulting dataset into sets of train, validation, and test, with a data percentage of %60, %25, and %15, respectively.

3.2 ProtoPNet Architecture & Configuration

ProtoPNet is a deep neural network based on the idea that, for image classification, an image can be decomposed into prototypical parts that can then be compared to similar parts of already known images. Its architecture (Fig. 1) includes three principal components: a classic CNN backbone, a prototypical layer and a dense layer.

Fig. 1. Architecture of the ProtoPNet network [2].

- **Convolutional Neural Network:** a classical CNN such as VGG [27], or ResNet [9], is used as the backbone of the network to extract latent representations of features.
- **Prototypical Layer:** compares the extracted feature vectors within the latent space to a set of learned prototypes, calculating the euclidean distance between a feature vector and each prototype to get the most similar examples.
- **Dense Layer:** the last component of the architecture is a fully connected layer which produces class probabilities given the similarity scores calculated in the prototypical layer.

Since ProtoPNet’s interpretability comes from comparing image features in the latent space produced by the backbone network, the selection of this backbone architecture is crucial for obtaining quality results in the final model. In addition, image preprocessing and augmentation settings, and hyperparameters such as the number of

prototypes per class, and the number of prototype update operations play a fundamental role in the development of the model. Thus, in order to get an optimal system, extensive experimentation is required with different model configurations.

Table 1. Configuration of the eight initial ProtoPNet models.

Model name	Backbone	Prototype Update Freq.	Pre-processing
VGG-5P	VGG-19	5 Epochs	Padding
VGG-5N	VGG-19	5 Epochs	Cropping
VGG-10P	VGG-19	10 Epochs	Padding
VGG-10N	VGG-19	10 Epochs	Cropping
ResNet-5P	ResNet-50	5 Epochs	Padding
ResNet-5N	ResNet-50	5 Epochs	Cropping
ResNet-10P	ResNet-50	10 Epochs	Padding
ResNet-10N	ResNet-50	10 Epochs	Cropping

For this work, we train the ProtoPNet model with eight different configurations before choosing the setup for the training of the final model. These eight models have the same base configuration as proposed by the original paper [2] but differ in the backbone network setting, the prototype update operation frequency and the pre-processing done to the images before training. Details for each model are presented in Table 1.

4 Results & Final Model

This section presents the outcomes of our experimental investigations aimed at applying ProtoPNet to object classification in railway environments. We detail the performance metrics and qualitative analysis obtained from evaluating various model configurations and data processing methodologies. Based on these outcomes, we identify and present the final model configuration chosen for achieving robust and interpretable classification within the challenging railway environment.

Table 2. Quantitative metrics of the eight initial ProtoPNet models.

Model name	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
VGG-5P	0.9247	0.7515	0.6914	0.7012
VGG-5N	0.9139	0.7064	0.6264	0.6471
VGG-10P	0.9103	0.7835	0.6831	0.7135
VGG-10N	0.9031	0.7525	0.6989	0.7088
ResNet-5P	0.9291	0.7584	0.6934	0.6995
ResNet-5N	0.9300	0.7812	0.6982	0.7278
ResNet-10P	0.9202	0.6855	0.7079	0.6582
ResNet-10N	0.9175	0.7459	0.7212	0.7114

Quantitative results of the eight initial models (Table 2) show that all of them achieve an *accuracy* over 0.9, with a maximum of 0.93 for the ResNet-5N model, measured in the validation set of the dataset. These metrics reveal that all tested configurations adapt well to the specifics of the railway domain. Nonetheless, there are

subtle differences between them, for instance, models with ResNet backbone generally achieve better accuracy than those with VGG.

In a traditional deep learning development loop, we could stop our analysis here and choose the model with the better performance. However, since ProtoPNet also learns easily interpretable image prototypes, we can perform a qualitative evaluation of those to check if learned features and concepts align with human-perceived features of the classified labels.

Fig. 2. Learned prototypes of the eight initial models for class *person*. Borders are colored green for prototypes that we consider present relevant information, orange for partial or low information and red for the ones that do not present information..

Qualitative exploration of the learned prototypes reveals that all eight configurations stand out negatively for the perceived quality of their prototypes (Fig. 2). All configurations suffer from the same effect that prototypes tend to converge into blurred, unfocused images or images with a great deal of padding. Looking into the model’s implementation, especially the prototype selection process, we can infer that these blurry prototypes are probably chosen because the augmented dataset contains a fair amount of grey-like blur and sometimes black padding, which will probably end up being very close to each other in the learned latent space.

In addition, configurations with the ResNet backbone tend to learn the same prototype several times, which introduces a lack of intra-class diversity issue to the final model. Models with VGG as a backbone network seem to learn more visually robust prototypes, especially in the configurations without padding.

Our hypothesis is that the models are suffering from an effect called shortcut learning, a known issue with deep learning models which occurs when the models learn patterns on the training set that lead them to better benchmark results, thus receiving

the name *shortcut*. However, this shortcut patterns or features do not align with real decisive features and result in models not performing well once they are deployed [8].

Fig. 3. Instances of the dataset from the *person* class with very small objects or no object at all.

Reflecting on these qualitative results and the possibility of shortcut learning, we take a step back and look into the issues the dataset could have introduced in our models:

- OSDaR23 is labelled in a very precise manner so even instances with very small bounding boxes ($< 15 \times 15$) are taken into account as a valid instance (Fig. 3).
- The augmentation process proposed by the original authors of ProtoPNet [2] performs some zoom-in operations on images that may further degrade the information quality on the final dataset (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Errors produced by the original data-augmentation process.

Thus, a new filtering and augmentation process is needed for the OSDaR23 dataset. We perform a manual filtering that removes images that are too blurry or images with very low information of objects. This process reduces the 5922-image dataset to 5227

images. Additionally, we use a new data augmentation process that only uses horizontal flips, small rotations and controlled cut-out operations.

Given the results discussed above, there is a need to balance out quantitative and qualitative analysis when it comes to selecting a final model for training with the new approach for data processing. While *ResNet-5N* achieves the best metrics in terms of accuracy and F1-score, we consider that *VGG-5N* is the most appropriate model because it combines balanced quantitative metrics while obtaining one of the best sets of learned prototypes, achieving high performance and interpretability at the same time.

With this chosen model (*VGG-5N*), we perform a final training and validation of the model with the manually filtered OSDaR23 dataset. For data augmentation, we train 3 different configurations as seen in Table 3.

Table 3. Quantitative evaluation of the final ProtoPNet model.

Augmentation Type	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
No augmentation	0.8833	0.5618	0.6231	0.5598
ProtoPNet augmentation	0.9054	0.6028	0.6059	0.5994
Ours	0.9000	0.7600	0.6678	0.6932

Quantitative results of this final model reveal that the original data augmentation process enhances the model’s performance in comparison to a model trained with no data augmentation. Our set of manually revised transformations proves to achieve a much higher performance in terms of *precision*, *recall* and *F1-score*.

Fig. 5. Learned prototypes of the final models for class *person*. Borders are colored green for prototypes that we consider present relevant information, orange for partial or low information and red for the ones that do not present information.

Regarding qualitative results (Fig. 5), we observe an overall enhancement of prototype quality in the non-augmented model and the model augmented with our manually defined augmentations, which further confirms that a careful selection of data filtering and augmentation is paramount.

5 Conclusions

This paper addressed the critical need for interpretable AI systems in the safety-critical railway environment, particularly for obstacle and pedestrian classification. Given the challenges posed by dynamic weather, illumination changes, cluttered backgrounds,

and motion blur, relying on black-box models is problematic for verification and trust. To tackle this, we proposed and systematically adapted the Prototypical Part Network (ProtoPNet), an inherently interpretable model that provides case-based explanations, for this specific application. Utilising the multi-sensor OSDaR23 dataset, we detailed our system architecture and experimental design, exploring various ProtoPNet configurations based on different backbones, prototype update frequencies, and initial pre-processing methods. Our initial experiments showed that all eight tested configurations achieved promising quantitative metrics, with an accuracy over 0.9. However, a crucial qualitative analysis of the learned prototypes revealed significant limitations, with prototypes often appearing blurred, unfocused, or heavily padded. This qualitative issue was linked to characteristics of the OSDaR23 dataset, including very small objects, and potential problems introduced by the original data augmentation process. The rapid detection of issues on learned prototypes demonstrated the enhancement ProtoPNet presents over traditional *black-box* models for development and debugging.

Recognising the importance of prototype quality for interpretability, we refined our data filtering and augmentation process, implementing manual filtering for low-information images and a new augmentation strategy. Based on the balance between quantitative performance and prototype interpretability, the VGG-5N configuration was selected as the most appropriate model for training with this improved data handling. Our final experiments demonstrated that training with our manually revised augmentation significantly enhanced key performance indicators such as precision, recall, and F1-score compared to training without augmentation or with the original ProtoPNet augmentation. This indicates that the improved data processing is crucial for achieving both high performance and better prototype quality.

Future work could extend this research in several directions. Exploring alternative strategies for handling very small objects in the dataset and further refining data augmentation techniques specifically tailored for railway imagery could yield additional improvements. Investigating methods to quantify prototype clarity more objectively could also provide valuable insights. Furthermore, integrating ProtoPNet into a complete object detection framework to provide interpretable localisation could enhance its utility in real-world railway applications. Finally, examining the effectiveness of the prototype-based explanations with domain experts could validate their utility for certification and debugging processes.

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References

1. Chattopadhyay, A., Sarkar, A., Howlader, P., Balasubramanian, V.N.: Grad-cam++: Generalized gradient-based visual explanations for deep convolutional networks. In: 2018 IEEE winter conference on applications of computer vision (WACV). pp. 839–847. IEEE (2018)

2. Chen, C., Li, O., Tao, D., Barnett, A., Rudin, C., Su, J.K.: This looks like that: deep learning for interpretable image recognition. *Advances in neural information processing systems* **32** (2019)
3. Cortes, C., Vapnik, V.: Support-vector networks. *Machine learning* **20**, 273–297 (1995)
4. Dalal, N., Triggs, B.: Histograms of oriented gradients for human detection. In: 2005 IEEE computer society conference on computer vision and pattern recognition (CVPR'05). vol. 1, pp. 886–893. Ieee (2005)
5. Debole, N., Barbiero, P., Giannini, F., Passeggini, A., Teso, S., Marconato, E.: If concept bottlenecks are the question, are foundation models the answer? *arXiv preprint arXiv:2504.19774* (2025)
6. Devireddy, K.: A comparative study of explainable ai methods: Model-agnostic vs. model-specific approaches. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2504.04276* (2025)
7. Dosovitskiy, A., Beyer, L., Kolesnikov, A., Weissenborn, D., Zhai, X., Unterthiner, T., Dehghani, M., Minderer, M., Heigold, G., Gelly, S., et al.: An image is worth 16x16 words: Transformers for image recognition at scale. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2010.11929* (2020)
8. Geirhos, R., Jacobsen, J.H., Michaelis, C., Zemel, R., Brendel, W., Bethge, M., Wichmann, F.A.: Shortcut learning in deep neural networks. *Nature Machine Intelligence* **2**(11), 665–673 (2020)
9. He, K., Zhang, X., Ren, S., Sun, J.: Deep residual learning for image recognition. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition*. pp. 770–778 (2016)
10. Hou, J., Liu, S., Bie, Y., Wang, H., Tan, A., Luo, L., Chen, H.: Self-explainable ai for medical image analysis: A survey and new outlooks. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2410.02331* (2024)
11. Kamakshi, V., Krishnan, N.C.: Explainable image classification: The journey so far and the road ahead. *AI* **4**, 620–651 (2023)
12. Kapoor, R., Goel, R., Sharma, A.: An intelligent railway surveillance framework based on recognition of object and railway track using deep learning. *Multimedia tools and applications* **81**, 21083–21109 (2022)
13. Kim, B., Wattenberg, M., Gilmer, J., Cai, C., Wexler, J., Viegas, F., et al.: Interpretability beyond feature attribution: Quantitative testing with concept activation vectors (tcav). In: *International conference on machine learning*. pp. 2668–2677. PMLR (2018)
14. Koh, P.W., Nguyen, T., Tang, Y.S., Mussmann, S., Pierson, E., Kim, B., Liang, P.: Concept bottleneck models. In: *International conference on machine learning*. pp. 5338–5348. PMLR (2020)
15. Liu, W., Anguelov, D., Erhan, D., Szegedy, C., Reed, S., Fu, C.Y., Berg, A.C.: Ssd: Single shot multibox detector. In: *Computer Vision—ECCV 2016: 14th European Conference, Amsterdam, The Netherlands, October 11–14, 2016, Proceedings, Part I 14*. pp. 21–37. Springer (2016)
16. Liu, Z., Lin, Y., Cao, Y., Hu, H., Wei, Y., Zhang, Z., Lin, S., Guo, B.: Swin transformer: Hierarchical vision transformer using shifted windows. In: *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF international conference on computer vision*. pp. 10012–10022 (2021)
17. Lundberg, S.M., Lee, S.I.: A unified approach to interpreting model predictions. In: Guyon, I., Luxburg, U.V., Bengio, S., Wallach, H., Fergus, R., Vishwanathan, S., Garnett, R. (eds.) *Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems 30*, pp. 4765–4774. Curran Associates, Inc. (2017)
18. Muhammad, M.B., Yeasin, M.: Eigen-cam: Class activation map using principal components. In: *2020 international joint conference on neural networks (IJCNN)*. pp. 1–7. IEEE (2020)
19. Oh, S.C., Kim, G.D., Jeong, W.T., Park, Y.T.: Vision-based object detection for passenger's safety in railway platform. In: *2008 International conference on control, automation and systems*. pp. 2134–2137. IEEE (2008)

20. Redmon, J., Divvala, S., Girshick, R., Farhadi, A.: You only look once: Unified, real-time object detection. In: Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition. pp. 779–788 (2016)
21. Ren, S., He, K., Girshick, R., Sun, J.: Faster r-cnn: Towards real-time object detection with region proposal networks. *Advances in neural information processing systems* **28** (2015)
22. Ribeiro, M.T., Singh, S., Guestrin, C.: "why should i trust you?" explaining the predictions of any classifier. In: Proceedings of the 22nd ACM SIGKDD international conference on knowledge discovery and data mining. pp. 1135–1144 (2016)
23. Ristić-Durrant, D., Franke, M., Michels, K.: A review of vision-based on-board obstacle detection and distance estimation in railways. *Sensors* **21**(10), 3452 (2021)
24. Rudin, C.: Stop explaining black box machine learning models for high stakes decisions and use interpretable models instead. *Nature Machine Intelligence* **1**, 206–215 (2019)
25. Sabnis, O.V., Lokeshkumar, R.: A novel object detection system for improving safety at unmanned railway crossings. In: 2019 Fifth International Conference on Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (ICONSTEM). vol. 1, pp. 149–152. IEEE (2019)
26. Selvaraju, R.R., Cogswell, M., Das, A., Vedantam, R., Parikh, D., Batra, D.: Grad-cam: Visual explanations from deep networks via gradient-based localization. In: Proceedings of the IEEE international conference on computer vision. pp. 618–626 (2017)
27. Simonyan, K., Zisserman, A.: Very deep convolutional networks for large-scale image recognition. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1409.1556* (2014)
28. Tagiew, R., Klasek, P., Tilly, R., Köppel, M., Denzler, P., Neumaier, P., Klockau, T., Boekhoff, M., Schwalbe, K.: Osdar23: Open sensor data for rail 2023. In: 8th International Conference on Robotics and Automation Engineering (ICRAE). p. 270–276. IEEE (2023)
29. Tang, R., De Donato, L., Besinović, N., Flammini, F., Goverde, R.M., Lin, Z., Liu, R., Tang, T., Vittorini, V., Wang, Z.: A literature review of artificial intelligence applications in railway systems. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies* **140**, 103679 (2022)
30. Viola, P., Jones, M.: Rapid object detection using a boosted cascade of simple features. In: Proceedings of the 2001 IEEE computer society conference on computer vision and pattern recognition. CVPR 2001. vol. 1, pp. I–I. Ieee (2001)
31. Winfield, A., Watson, E.N.: How to make autonomous systems more transparent and trustworthy (2022)